

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 20-oktabrdagi “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PF-6084-sonli Farmoniga muvofiq “2020-2030-yillarda o‘zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi”da belgilangan vazifalarning ijrosini ta’minlash maqsadida hamda Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligining 2024-yil 27-dekabrda 490-sonli buyrug‘iga asosan **Guliston davlat universitetida 2025-yil 29-30-sentabr kunlari** o‘tkazilgan **“TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI”** mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. Anjuman zamonaviy tilshunoslikning eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzulari va amaliy masalalariga doir uslubiy ishlanmalarni aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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olinadi. Shu bois, o'qitish jarayonida har bir leksik birlik fonida unga bog'liq tarixiy-madaniyatning qisqacha sharhini berish, multimediali va interfaol amaliyotlar tashkil etish lozim.

Shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, ekvivalentsiz leksika til va madaniyatning ajralmas bo'lagi sifatida chet tillari o'qitishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bunday leksik birliklarning o'ziga xosligi va ma'nolarini to'g'ri yetkazib berish qiyinchiliklarini hal qilishda pedagogik texnologiyalar katta rol o'ynaydi. Xususan, multimedia va interfaol mashqlar, zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya vositalari yordamida olib borilgan o'qitish ekvivalentsiz leksikaning o'zlashtirilishini sezilarli darajada osonlashtirdi. Ma'ruza va yozma izohlarga qaraganda, vizual va eshitish materiallari bilan boyitilgan darslar o'quvchilarning tushunchalarni idrok etish darajasini oshiradi. Bu esa ingliz tilidagi ekvivalentlari bo'lmagan leksik birliklarni mashg'ulotda jonli misollar bilan qo'llashning samaradorligini oshiradi. Buning natijasida o'quvchilarda tilning milliy kechmishga oid xususiyatini anglash va chet tilini o'rgatishda tarjimonlik salohiyatini oshirish yo'lida sezilarli yutuqlarni kuzatish mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitishda pedagogik texnologiyalarga alohida e'tibor qaratish talab etiladi. O'qitishning an'anaviy metodlariga yangi texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish leksik birliklarni samarali o'rgatish va til bilish doirasini kengaytirishga imkon beradi. Shu munosabat bilan kelajakda maktab va oliy ta'lim jarayonlarida ekvivalentsiz leksikani o'qitish metodikalarini yanada takomillashtirib, raqamli resurslar yaratish istiqbollari joriy etilishi lozimligini ta'kidlash muhim.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRADE TERMINOLOGY IN SPECIALIZED SUBLANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article examines English and Uzbek trade terminology within the specialized sublanguages of law, economics, and finance. Legal discourse

demonstrates stability and semantic rigidity, while economic and financial discourse reveal openness to borrowings, calques, and neologisms. Comparative analysis highlights both similarities, such as the widespread use of internationalisms and acronyms, and differences, including semantic precision in English versus greater flexibility in Uzbek.

Key words and phrases: specialized sublanguages, legal, economic and financial discourse, translation studies, lexicography, ESP.

The study of specialized sublanguages has gained increasing importance in modern linguistics, particularly as professional communication becomes more globalized and terminologically complex. Trade, as a domain of law, economics, and finance, relies on a highly specialized vocabulary that serves not only as a tool of professional interaction but also as a reflection of socio-economic development. According to Lotte, terminology forms the skeleton of scientific and technical knowledge [Lotte, 1961, p. 160]. Building on this view, in the field of trade such a role is even more pronounced, since terminological precision directly affects contractual relations, financial transactions, and market regulations.

In English linguistics, scholars such as Jennifer Pearson [Pearson, 1998, p. 242] and Cabré [Cabré, 1999, p. 248] have emphasized that specialized sublanguages are defined by functional and pragmatic features that differentiate them from general vocabulary. In the Uzbek context, Oybek Ahmedov has conducted research on taxation terminology highlighting its historical roots, semantic development, and the impact of borrowings and internationalisms [Ahmedov, 2016, p. 255]. Given that taxation represents a crucial subdomain of economic and trade discourse, his findings are highly relevant for understanding the dynamics of Uzbek trade-related lexicon in general.

Specialized vocabulary, often referred to as terminology, represents the lexical foundation of professional communication. Unlike general vocabulary, which is characterized by broad usage and semantic flexibility, specialized vocabulary is marked by precision, consistency, and functional restriction to particular domains of knowledge. Cabré argues that specialized vocabulary represents the linguistic realization of concepts belonging to particular domains of expertise, and therefore functions both as a communicative resource and as part of a structured conceptual system [Cabré, 1999, p. 248]. In this sense, trade terminology can be considered a subset of specialized vocabulary that has developed in close connection with the evolution of commerce, law, economics, and finance.

The characteristics of trade terms derive from their dual nature as both linguistic and socio-economic entities. On the one hand, they must maintain semantic accuracy, since the misinterpretation of a single term in legal or financial documents can lead to serious consequences. On the other hand, they reflect the dynamics of socio-economic life, which explains the openness of trade terminology to borrowings, calques, and neologisms. In English, expressions such as *outsourcing*, *e-commerce*, or *derivative markets* illustrate how the field rapidly absorbs innovations, while in

Uzbek, terms like *eksport*, *import*, and *aksiya* show the impact of international borrowings on local discourse.

Previous research on specialized sublanguages and trade vocabulary has taken different approaches. In Western linguistics, scholars such as Pearson [Pearson, 1998, p. 242] and Bhatia [Bhatia, 1993, p. 246] have explored the pragmatic and discourse functions of specialized terms, emphasizing that terminology not only encodes concepts but also constructs professional identity. In Uzbek linguistics, significant contributions have been made by Nilufar Atayeva [Atayeva, 2020, p. 167] and Yekaterina Shirinova [Shirinova, 2020, p. 152], who have investigated the development of banking and financial terminology as a core component of trade discourse. These works highlight both the semantic and functional shifts that occur when specialized terms enter Uzbek from global economic contexts and provide a foundation for understanding the dynamics of trade-related vocabulary more broadly.

Trade terminology cannot be regarded as a single unified lexical field. It develops and operates within several specialized sublanguages, most importantly those of law, economics and finance. Each of these domains places specific demands on language and fulfills distinct communicative functions, and these factors shape both the structure and the usage of trade-related vocabulary.

In **the legal sublanguage**, trade terms are characterized by precision, stability, and resistance to change. This can be observed in English through expressions such as *contract of sale*, *arbitration clause*, or *breach of agreement*, which retain their form and meaning across decades of usage. Similarly, Uzbek legal terminology maintains strict boundaries of interpretation in terms like *savdo shartnomasi* or *kelishuv shartlari*. The conservative nature of legal trade terms arises from their role in regulating rights and obligations, where ambiguity could lead to misinterpretation and disputes. Thus, legal terminology functions as a stabilizing force in the broader system of trade vocabulary.

The economic sublanguage, by contrast, demonstrates a higher degree of openness and adaptability. Economic discourse often absorbs new terms that describe evolving processes, policies, or institutions. In English, terms such as *liberalization*, *outsourcing*, or *trade barriers* highlight the interaction between economics and international relations, while Uzbek equivalents like *liberalizatsiya* and *bozor islohotlari* reflect the influence of global market reforms on local linguistic practice. Uzbek economic terminology has been significantly shaped by the transition to a market economy, which required the adoption of new conceptual categories largely introduced through borrowings and calques.

The financial sublanguage represents perhaps the most dynamic sphere of trade terminology. Financial markets are inherently innovative, producing a constant flow of new instruments, practices, and technologies that demand corresponding lexical representation. English financial discourse, with terms like *derivatives* or *cryptocurrency*, demonstrates the creative capacity of language to name and categorize emerging phenomena. Uzbek financial terminology has responded to these changes with borrowings such as *derivativ* and *kriptovalyuta*, while also employing native resources in expressions like *moliya bozori* or *qimmatli qog'ozlar*.

A comparison of English and Uzbek trade terminology across legal, economic, and financial sublanguages reveals both points of convergence and divergence, shaped by historical experience, linguistic traditions, and the degree of integration into global markets.

One of the clearest similarities is the shared reliance on internationalisms, particularly in economic and financial discourse. Terms such as *export*, *import*, and *inflation* in English correspond directly to *eksport*, *import*, and *inflyatsiya* in Uzbek. These parallels demonstrate the impact of globalization, which has led to the international circulation of trade-related concepts and their lexical equivalents. Both languages also exhibit extensive use of **abbreviations** and **acronyms**. English employs forms like *WTO* (*World Trade Organization*) or *FTA* (*Free Trade Agreement*), while Uzbek uses *JST* (*Jahon Savdo Tashkiloti*) and *EIH* (*erkin iqtisodiy hudud*). The pragmatic motivation here is universal: to increase communicative efficiency in highly technical environments.

At the same time, differences emerge in the degree of semantic precision and lexical flexibility. English trade terminology, particularly in legal sublanguage, tends to maintain rigid conceptual boundaries. Phrases such as *consideration* or *breach of contract* carry specialized meanings that cannot be replaced by near synonyms without legal consequences. By contrast, Uzbek legal terminology, while striving for accuracy, often allows broader semantic variation. For instance, *kelishuv* may refer to both a formal agreement and a more general understanding, depending on context. This flexibility can be advantageous in oral communication but presents challenges in translation and international documentation, where exact equivalence is required.

Another significant difference lies in the strategies of lexical expansion. **English** frequently generates new terms through **compounding** and **derivation** (*countertrade*, *underpricing*), while **Uzbek** relies heavily on **borrowings** and **calques** (*qarama-qarshi savdo*, *past baholash*). Uzbek economic discourse in the post-Soviet period has shown a preference for adopting foreign lexical items rather than creating neologisms from native roots. This has resulted in a hybrid system where native and borrowed elements coexist, but with borrowings dominating in financial and technological contexts.

From an applied perspective, these similarities and differences have practical consequences for translation, lexicography, and ESP teaching. Translators must navigate the gap between English semantic rigidity and Uzbek semantic elasticity, ensuring both accuracy and cultural acceptability. Lexicographers face the task of documenting not only direct borrowings but also local adaptations, creating dictionaries that reflect the dynamic interplay between global and national terminology. In teaching ESP, educators must prepare students to understand both international trade terminology and its Uzbek equivalents, highlighting cases where direct equivalence is absent or misleading.

Overall, the comparative analysis shows that while English and Uzbek trade terminology share a common global foundation, they diverge in their semantic organization, strategies of expansion, and functional flexibility. These differences underline the necessity of contextual and interdisciplinary approaches to studying

specialized sublanguages, especially in a world where trade communication increasingly crosses linguistic boundaries.

The analysis of trade terminology across legal, economic, and financial sublanguages demonstrates that specialized vocabulary functions as a layered and stratified system rather than a uniform lexical field. The comparative perspective highlights both convergences and divergences. English and Uzbek share a common reliance on internationalisms and abbreviations, shaped by the realities of global trade communication. At the same time, English legal and financial terminology tends to display semantic rigidity and morphological creativity, whereas Uzbek terminology is characterized by semantic flexibility and a higher dependence on borrowings and calques. These patterns point to different strategies of linguistic adaptation within specialized sublanguages.

On the whole, these insights confirm that trade terminology in specialized sublanguages is a dynamic system where stability and change coexist, shaped by the dual pressures of professional communication and globalization.

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